

Supplementary Figure 1. Studies of B6-Thr92-Dio2 (Thr) and B6-Ala92-Dio2 (Ala) mice (n=4-7 per group) placed on a chow or HFD. **(A)** Initial body weight, **(B)** Body weight gain over time. Values are expressed as the mean \pm SEM. HFD indicates high-fat diet.

CLAMS 14 weeks on HFD

Supplementary Figure 2. Studies of B6-Thr92-Dio2 (Thr) and B6-Ala92-Dio2 (Ala) mice (n=at least 4 per group) placed on a chow or HFD. **(A-C)** Indirect calorimetry; **(A)** VO₂, oxygen consumption, **(B)** Heat, **(C)** RER and the **(D)** calculated contribution of fat oxidation to energy expenditure. Values are individually expressed or as mean ± SEM. HFD indicates high-fat diet; RER indicates respiratory exchange ratio=RQ.

Suppl. Figure 2

Supplementary Figure 3. Studies of B6-Thr92-Dio2 (Thr) and B6-Ala92-Dio2 (Ala) mice (n=6-10 per group) placed on a chow or HFD. **(A)** Fasting glucose (mg/dL). **(B)** Glucose tolerance test – GTT; **(C)** area under the curve AUC; **(D)** insulin tolerance test – ITT; **(E)** Area under the curve (AUC). Values are expressed as mean ± SEM. *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001. HFD indicates high-fat diet.

Supplementary Figure 4. Studies of B6-Thr92-Dio2 (Thr) and B6-Ala92-Dio2 (Ala) mice (n=7-10 per group) placed on a chow or HFD. **(A)** Weight of epididymal, subcutaneous, and retroperitoneal WAT pads; **(B)** WAT index; **(C)** weight of the interscapular BAT. Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM. *p<0.05, **p<0.01, *** p<0.001, ****p<0.0001. HFD indicates high-fat diet; WAT indicates white adipose tissue; BAT indicates brown adipose tissue.

A**Suppl. Figure 5**

Supplementary Figure 5. Studies of B6-Thr92-Dio2 (Thr) and B6-Ala92-Dio2 (Ala) mice (n=7-10 per group) placed on a chow or HFD. **(A)** Liver weight; **(B)** images of the liver immediately after the animals were euthanized; Representative image of liver histology from **(C)** B6-Thr92-Dio2 mouse. **(D)** B6-Ala92-Dio2 mouse. **(E)** B6-Thr92-Dio2 mouse on HFD. **(F)** B6-Ala92-Dio2 mouse on HFD. Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. HFD indicates a high-fat diet. QuPath generated scale bars = 50 μ m; magnification is x40.

Supplementary Figure 7. iBAT RNAseq analysis of FVB-Ala92-Dio2 (Ala) vs FVB-Thr92-Dio2 (Thr) mice (n=3 per group). Autophagy pathway. Color blue indicates down-regulated genes and color red indicates overexpressed genes. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA, $p < 0.05$ and $FDR < 0.25$. iBAT indicates interscapular brown adipose tissue.

Suppl. Figure 7

Supplementary Figure 8. iBAT RNAseq analysis of FVB-Ala92-Dio2 (Ala) vs FVB-Thr92-Dio2 (Thr) mice (n=3 per group). Protein processing in endoplasmic reticulum pathway. Color blue indicates down-regulated genes and color red indicates overexpressed genes. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA, $p < 0.05$ and $FDR < 0.25$ iBAT indicates interscapular brown adipose tissue.

Suppl. Figure 8

Supplementary Figure 9. iBAT RNAseq analysis of FVB-Ala92-Dio2 (Ala) vs FVB-Thr92-Dio2 (Thr) mice (n=3 per group). Parkinson's disease pathway. Color blue indicates down-regulated genes and color red indicates overexpressed genes. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA, $p < 0.05$ and $FDR < 0.25$ iBAT indicates interscapular brown adipose tissue.

Supplementary Figure 10. iBAT RNAseq analysis of FVB-Ala92-Dio2 (Ala) vs FVB-Thr92-Dio2 (Thr) mice (n=3 per group). Alzheimer's disease pathway. Color blue indicates down-regulated genes and color red indicates overexpressed genes. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA, $p < 0.05$ and $FDR < 0.25$. iBAT indicates interscapular brown adipose tissue.

Suppl. Figure 10

Supplementary Figure 11. iBAT RNAseq analysis of FVB-Ala92-Dio2 (Ala) vs FVB-Thr92-Dio2 (Thr) mice (n=3 per group). Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis pathway. Color blue indicates down-regulated genes and color red indicates overexpressed genes. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA, $p < 0.05$ and $FDR < 0.25$. iBAT indicates interscapular brown adipose tissue.

Supplementary Figure 12. iBAT RNAseq analysis of FVB-Ala92-Dio2 (Ala) vs FVB-Thr92-Dio2 (Thr) mice (n=3 per group). Prion disease pathway. Color blue indicates down-regulated genes and color red indicates overexpressed genes. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA, $p < 0.05$ and $FDR < 0.25$. iBAT indicates interscapular brown adipose tissue.

Suppl. Figure 12

Supplementary Figure 13. iBAT RNAseq analysis of FVB-Ala92-Dio2 (Ala) vs FVB-Thr92-Dio2 (Thr) mice (n=3 per group). Huntington's disease pathway. Color blue indicates down-regulated genes and color red indicates overexpressed genes. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA, p<0.05 and FDR<0.25. iBAT indicates interscapular brown adipose tissue.

APOPTOSIS

Supplementary Figure 14. iBAT RNaseq analysis of FVB-Ala92-Dio2 (Ala) vs FVB-Thr92-Dio2 (Thr) mice (n=3 per group). Apoptosis pathway. Color blue indicates down-regulated genes and color red indicates overexpressed genes. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA, $p < 0.05$ and $FDR < 0.25$. iBAT indicates interscapular brown adipose tissue.

Suppl. Figure 14

INSULIN SIGNALING PATHWAY

Supplementary Figure 15. iBAT RNAseq analysis of FVB-Ala92-Dio2 (Ala) vs FVB-Thr92-Dio2 (Thr) mice (n=3 per group). Insulin signaling pathway. Color blue indicates down-regulated genes and color red indicates overexpressed genes. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA, $p < 0.05$ and $FDR < 0.25$. iBAT indicates interscapular brown adipose tissue.

Suppl. Figure 15

AMPK SIGNALING PATHWAY

Supplementary Figure 16. iBAT RNaseq analysis of FVB-Ala92-Dio2 (Ala) vs FVB-Thr92-Dio2 (Thr) mice (n=3 per group). AMPK signaling pathway. Color blue indicates down-regulated genes and color red indicates overexpressed genes. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA, $p < 0.05$ and $FDR < 0.25$. iBAT indicates interscapular brown adipose tissue.

mTOR SIGNALING PATHWAY

Supplementary Figure 17. iBAT RNAseq analysis of FVB-Ala92-Dio2 (Ala) vs FVB-Thr92-Dio2 (Thr) mice (n=3 per group). mTOR signaling pathway. Color blue indicates down-regulated genes and color red indicates overexpressed genes. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA, $p < 0.05$ and $FDR < 0.25$. iBAT indicates interscapular brown adipose tissue.

Suppl. Figure 17

THYROID HORMONE SIGNALING PATHWAY

Supplementary Figure 18. iBAT RNAseq analysis of FVB-Ala92-Dio2 (Ala) vs FVB-Thr92-Dio2 (Thr) mice (n=3 per group). Thyroid hormone signaling pathway. Color blue indicates down-regulated genes and color red indicates overexpressed genes. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA, $p < 0.05$ and $FDR < 0.25$. iBAT indicates interscapular brown adipose tissue.

NOTCH SIGNALING PATHWAY

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Supplementary Figure 19. iBAT RNAseq analysis of FVB-Ala92-Dio2 (Ala) vs FVB-Thr92-Dio2 (Thr) mice (n=3 per group). Notch signaling pathway. Color blue indicates down-regulated genes and color red indicates overexpressed genes. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA, $p < 0.05$ and $FDR < 0.25$. iBAT indicates interscapular brown adipose tissue.

Supplementary Figure 20. iBAT RNAseq analysis of FVB-Ala92-Dio2 (Ala) vs FVB-Thr92-Dio2 (Thr) mice (n=3 per group). HIF-1 signaling pathway. Color blue indicates down-regulated genes and color red indicates overexpressed genes. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA, $p < 0.05$ and $FDR < 0.25$. iBAT indicates interscapular brown adipose tissue.

Supplementary Figure 21. iBAT RNAseq analysis of FVB-Ala92-Dio2 (Ala) vs FVB-Thr92-Dio2 (Thr) mice (n=3 per group). Glucagon signaling pathway. Color blue indicates down-regulated genes and color red indicates overexpressed genes. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA, $p < 0.05$ and $FDR < 0.25$. iBAT indicates interscapular brown adipose tissue.